

EVOLUTION OF PANCHAYAT RAJ INSTITUTION AND BACKWARD CASTE POLITICAL PARTICIPATIONS IN ANDHRA PRADESH

Dr. M. Akshutha Nandh
Lecturer in Political Science,
SVGM.Government Degree College
Kalyandurg

Abstract: This article presents a narrative of what the local self-government is all about, how it originated in the past and how it happened to be a critical entity in the local administration in the bygone era and how it played a very defining role till the end of the Mogul period and how it was transformed and started losing its relevance giving the British era. After independence, the governments of the day took into cognizance the importance of local self-government in the improving of the countryside and how various efforts are made by the governments of the day in the post independence era to accord due importance to the local self-government and how various committees like Balwant Roy Mehta committee, Ashok Mehta committee, G.V.K Rao Committee, L.M. Singhvi's Committee, R.S. Sarkaria Commission Report Dr. P.K Thungon Committee, The A.P Gram Panchayati Raj Act, etc. were appointed to see into the working and give appropriate suggestions and recommendations for the effective functioning of the local self-government. It also presents a picture of the empowerment of the Local Government after the 73rd and 74th Constitutional Amendments which are made to the Indian Constitution. This chapter also throws light on the fact that the 73rd amendment which gave Constitutional sanctity to the reservations in the Local Bodies has enabled the enhancement of the representation of the backward classes in the local bodies in the elections that were conducted in 2001, 2006 and 2014 and how there has been steady increase in the representation of the backward classes in these local bodies ever since this amendment was brought into force. Similarly, Review of Literature, the objective of the study, the hypotheses along with the methodology, Sample Design, Need of the study, Scope of the study, that is adopted for the sake of this study is also discussed

KEY WORDS :- Panchayat Raj Institutions, Andhra Pradesh, Backward Castes, Political Participation, Rural Governance, Evolution, Marginalized Communities, India.73 and 74 constitution amendment in Indian Constitution, Backward castes reservations

Evolution of Panchayat Raj in Andhra Pradesh

In 1953, the pattern of local self government in Andhra State had been modelled on Madras State local self government institution. The Madras District Municipalities Act, 1920, the Madras District Boards Act, 1920, and Madras Village Panchayaties Act, 1950, comprised all the regulations for the local bodies.

In 1953, three types of rural local self government institutions were prevalent in the State. They are (i) District Boards, (ii) Taluk Boards and (iii) Village Panchayaties. The Village Panchayats were grouped under Class I and Class II according to population and income. A Panchayat having a population of not less than 5000 and an annual income of not less than Rs. 10,000 is per under class I Panchayat. The rest were categorised

under class II Panchayats. The number of Class I and Class II Panchayats, was 193 and 3687 respectively in 1956.

Adult citizens exercised their franchise raising their hands under joint electoral system. But, later the situation was changed by following secret ballot method. Responsibility for all developmental activities at the village level has been given to the Panchayats. Functions of the Panchayats are mentioned. These are related to the promotion and development of elementary education, cottage industries, promotion of agriculture, organization of collective farming and co-operative management of lands, establishment and maintenance of maternity and child welfare centres, developing wards, assisting for implementation of land reforms measures and forming programmes of production for the village. They got 7.5 percent of the revenue from the sources of land revenue. For the rest they depend on the grants sanctioned by the Union and the State Governments.

These elected institutions are endowed with powers and functions to perform useful work, especially for district and taluk boards. However, they had certain limitations too. Large Jurisdiction of district and taluk boards, absence of organic linkages between government departments and district boards, inadequate financial resources, ill equipped and poorly staged and insufficient technical and guidance from government departments, are some of the major lacunae found in the PRIs.

After independence, the introduction of Community Development (C.D) projects in 1952 and the National Extension Services (N.E.S) led to the extension of developing activities in rural areas. Besides, elaborative administrative machinery, advisory bodies at the block and district levels were formed to get the cooperation of the people. The Members of Legislative Assembly and Members of Parliament from the respective areas and some nominated members were associated with the advisory bodies. In spite of the existence of these advisory bodies at block and district levels, much of the planning and execution of developing work was done by administration.²⁴ The development of Panchayati Raj Institutions (PRIs) in the state can broadly be studied under four phases. They are;

The First Phase: 1959-65

The Government of Andhra Pradesh approved the recommendations of the Balwanth Roy Mehta (1957) Committee. It decided to establish one Panchayati Samiti in each district on an adhoc basis. The committee was benefited by the experience it gained through the working of Panchayat raj system and it brought forward legislation thereafter to create a three-tier system of Panchayati Raj. As the adhoc samiti was formed in 1958 and proved to be successful, the Andhra Pradesh Panchayati Samities and Zilla Parishads Act, 1959, was passed and by the end of 1959 these statutory elected bodies have been established in all the districts: the Panchayati Samities by November and the Zilla Parishads by end of 1959.

The 1959 Act

The first phase of statutory Panchayati Samities was constituted with the inauguration of the Shadnagar Block on 11th October, 1959 by Jawaharlal Nehru, the Prime Minister of India, (who inaugurated Panchayat Raj in India on 2nd October, 1959 in Rajasthan). By the end of November 1959, a total of 235 Panchayat Samities were established. The second and third batches were constituted later on in the next year.²⁵

At the time of the passing of the 1959 Act, the statutory village panchayats in the Andhra area had already been constituted under the Madras Village Panchayaties Act, 1950, while Gram Panchayaties existed in the Telangana area under the Hyderabad Village Panchayaties Act. With the existence of Panchayati Samities

and Zilla Parishads, all the three bodies at the village, block and district level became corporate, statutory and representative bodies. They could acquire, hold and dispose off property and enter into contracts.

In December 1959, all the twenty district boards were statutorily abolished and Zilla Parishads were constituted in their place. An adoptive order was issued to suitably adapt and transfer the powers, functions, assets and liabilities and also the institutions and staff of the district boards to the Panchayat Samities and Zilla Parishads. The Act of 1959 was amended in 1963. It had redefined the Andhra area, restricted the Membership of the Legislators with voting right to one Samiti only, and prohibited being a legislator and a presiding member for a person of any one of these bodies. It also enabled the Members of Legislative Assembly (M.L.As) to act as being the ex-officials members of the Zilla Parishad or Samiti if their constituencies included any rural area. It also prescribed the terms of the presiding members and forbid village officers from becoming members of these bodies.

In 1963, the government had deliberated the necessity to retain the full complement of staff as it existed in the 448 Samiti blocks. It had tried to assess, with a view to enunciate economy in spending expenditure on the establishment of Samithies. It has also decided to reduce the number of blocks for carving out larger blocks without affecting the tempo of developing activities.

A high power committee was set up under the chairmanship of M.Purushottam Pai to look into proto-related aspects. This Committee recommended that the Panchayati Samiti blocks were essential units of planning and development. It felt that panchayats were envisaged as instruments of economic progress and social change. There is a widest scope for the expression of democratic opinion at the village level, Big blocks would be financially stronger with increased scope for independent planning and execution of development programmes, those under the "Area Planning".

The Committee also suggested for the categorization of blocks as advanced, ordinary, backward and tribal, and the abolition of the distinction between Stage-I, Stage-II, Post-Stage, and so on. It recommended for the allotment of community development funds on varying per capita basis so that less developed blocks could get little more funds than others. Following these recommendations, an amendment was made to the 1959 Act in 1964 to strengthen the government to alter the boundaries of the blocks and reconstitute the Samitis. By July 1964, the number of blocks had been reduced from 448 to 321. In 1964 some town Municipalities in Telangana were also downgraded as Gram Panchayats. The Samiti blocks in the state were categorized as advanced, ordinary, backward and tribal by taking into consideration of per capita revenue, percentage of the irrigated area in the total area, literacy rate, and percentage of children attending schools and road mileage and others.

The A.P Gram Panchayati Raj Act, 1964 : The Andhra Pradesh Gram Panchayati Raj Act, 1964, superseded the previous Gram Panchayati Acts of Andhra and Telangana. Under this Act, the pattern was set up for future structure of Panchayati Raj in the state. Every village had to consist of a Gram Sabha and met at least twice a year to consider the annual statement of accounts and audit, the report of the administration of the previous year, the programme of works for the year ahead, and the proposals for fresh taxation or for enhancement of existing taxes. Usually the Sarpanch will preside over the Gram Panchayat. It is presided over by the deputy sarpanch, when the sarpanch is absent.

The Gram Panchayat is the premier institution of the people at the village level. Each village, with a population of ten thousand or above, will have a panchayat. When the population is below the above number, the villages are conveniently grouped. The total members of the Gram Panchayat are elected by all the voters of

the village. The total number of Panchayats varied from five to seventeen, depending upon the total population of the village. One seat will be reserved for women if the total strength of panchayati members was seven or less, and two seats if the total was nine or more. One seat was reserved either for the Scheduled Castes or the Scheduled Tribes (STs). Each village will be classified into many wards on the basis of population. The sarpanch and the Deputy-sarpanch are elected indirectly by the members of the panchayat. The term of office will be five years.

The Sarpanch is the executive head of the Gram Panchayat. He convenes and conducts the meeting of Gram Panchayat every month. He exercises administrative control over the executive officer who was in charge of more than one Panchayat. Besides the executive officer, the administrative personnel of the village comprise a *gram sevak* for four to six villages and a primary school teacher.

The 1964 Act had provided for functional committees for agriculture, public health, sanitation and communication, and also one or two other committees, if necessary. Works relating to agriculture, irrigation, drainage, co-operative, animal husbandry, civic amenities, education, public health, and rural arts and crafts were mentioned in the Act. Although under the statute the Gram Panchayat was assigned an important function, it played a key role in developing programmes. The success of these programmes depended upon the availability of financial resources. Adequate financial resources were a real problem for the panchayats.

For providing justice in civil and criminal cases, *Nyaya* panchayaties were established with a group of three to five villages under one *Nyaya* Panchayati. Their term of office was three years.

Panchayati Samiti

Till 1965 every Panchayat Samiti comprised all the sarpanches of the Gram Panchayats within its jurisdiction. The Members of Legislative Assembly and Members of Legislative Council representing the constituency acted as the ex-official members. After July 1964, an amendment was made to the A.P Panchayat Raj Act, 1959. It imposed restriction on the Members of the State Legislature from holding the Presidentship and Vice-Presidentship of the Panchayati Samits. However, if they wish to assume the office of the President or Vice-president they shall cease to be the Members of the State Legislature.

The State Government is empowered to extend the term of the President and Vice-President up to six months. It can remove them while in office, if there is a sufficient evidence of misuse of their office. Ex-officio members will hold their office as long as they continue to be Sarpanches, or Members of the State Legislature. The President of the Samiti could exercise administrative control over the Block Development Officer (B.D.O). He convenes the Panchayat Samithi meetings. He presides over the meetings and conducts them with dignity and decorum. The Panchayat Samit meets at least once in three months. The B.D.O. is the chief executive officer of the meeting of Panchayat Samithi. He is responsible for implementing its resolutions and those of the standing committee. He attends the meetings. He is not entitled to vote or to move any resolution.

The functions endowed with the Panchayati Samiti under the Andhra Pradesh Panchayat Samities and Zilla Parishads Act, 1959, was comprehensive and the same as those of Gram Panchayats. The Panchayati Samit is expected to perform every work concerned with the development of the local economy and infrastructure.

Zilla Parishad

There will be a Zilla Parishad for every district under the A.P Panchayat Raj Act, 1959. The Zilla Parishad consisted of the President (ex-officio) of each Panchayati Samiti in the district, the District Collector, the M.L.As and the Members of Legislative Council (M.L.Cs) from the district. Besides, it comprised the M.Ps elected from the district, two women representatives, and one representative from the S.C.s, and one from the S.Ts (if the population of the latter two categories was less than 5 percent of its total population in the district). If the population of the S.Ts was less than this percentage, another representative from the S.Cs was included, as well as two persons who are interested in rural development.

The Members of the Zilla Parishad will elect its Chairperson and Vice-Chairperson. The amendment which took place to the Act of 1959 and in 1963 brought an important change by imposing a ban on the District Collector from becoming the Chairperson of the Zilla Parishad. The Members of either House of the State Legislature or the Union Parliament were eligible to be elected as the chairpersons of the Zilla Parishad. However, they ceased to be the members of the former institutions if they were elected and wished to work with the district body.

The Chairperson of the Zilla Parishad convened, presided over and conducted all its meetings and exercised administrative control over the secretary. If the office of the Chairperson was vacant or if he had been continuously absent from the district for more than fifteen days, his powers and functions during the period of absence are entrusted with the Vice-president.

The 1959 Act enabled the Zilla Parishad to function as an advisory and supervisory body over the Panchayati Samities by endowing with powers to approve their budgets, coordinate their plans and distribute Funds (given by the government) among the blocks. It had also been allocated a few developmental functions, such as establishing, maintaining and expanding of secondary, vocational and industrial schools.

System of the Committees

The Panchayati institutions carried their functions with the help of several committees at various levels. The Panchayat Samiti, being a large body, worked during the first phase (1959-65) through seven standing committees, that is, planning and production, cooperatives and industries, education, women's welfare, communications, social welfare, taxation and finance. Each standing committee consisted of seven members, with some reservations for women and the deprived sections included in its structure. Similarly, general policies were discussed in all the sections of the Zilla Parishad, its work was also carried out through seven standing committees, which were the same for the Panchayati Samiti. Each standing committee of the Zilla Parishad comprised nine members, except the standing committee for education which had ten members.

Resources

The resources of the Gram Panchayat were derived from the government's grants, taxes and non-tax revenue, property and other miscellaneous sources, (as per the Andhra Pradesh Gram Panchayati Raj Act 1964). The Panchayat Samiti is empowered to levy a surcharge on land/local cess and on taxes levied by Panchayats. Contributions from Panchayats were the main source of income of the Gram Panchayat.

The main resources of the Zilla Parishad were Central or State Governmental funds, grants for development of cottage and small-scale industries, shares of land and local cess, state taxes or fees, income from endowments or trusts, and donations and contributions from the Panchayati Samiti and from the public in any form.

The Second Phase: 1965-70

In view of mounting criticism from various sections, including legislators against Panchayat Raj institutions, the Andhra Pradesh Congress Legislature party constituted a Committee in March 1968 to consider all aspects relating to Panchayati raj and to suggest necessary amendments to the concerned Act. It had twelve M.L.As as Members, while J.Vengala Rao, Ex-President of the Andhra Pradesh State Chamber of Panchayat Raj was the Convener.

J. Vengala Rao Committee

The Vengala Rao Committee identified certain factors that accounted for public dissatisfaction with Panchayat Raj. It pointed out that Panchayat Raj had the following drawbacks.

- a) Panchayat Raj lost its dynamism mainly due to paucity of funds.
- b) That it had a mode of constitution of different tiers and pattern of elections.
- c) It lacks functional freedom. Further, the committee felt that strengthening the hands of the bureaucracy at the district level had demoralised the entire set up. Lack of autonomy also made fun of the concept of local self-government.

The Committee made the following recommendations:

- i. M.Ps and M.L.As should be prohibited from holding elective posts in the two lower tiers, while they could have membership in the Zilla Parishads but without right to vote.
- ii. The Sarpanch, the Samiti President and the Chairperson of the Zilla Parishad should not have any independent powers and act strictly in accordance with the decisions of the committees of the respective bodies.
- iii. Use of party symbols should not to be permitted in elections at any level.
- iv. There is need (a) to provide the panchayats with adequate resources, (b) to eliminate their perpetual dependence on the government for funds. For this purpose, governmental lands, road margins, tank bunds, fisheries and other areas which come under the territory of Panchayats ought to be handed over for plantation and other income generated activities.³⁶

The major recommendation of the committee to improve the position of the Zilla Parishads annual income and grants-in-aid given to them should be raised from 25 paise to one rupee. Very meager changes were made in the Panchayati Raj structure during the second phase. In 1970, a new district of Ongole and a new taluk, Gajapathinagaram in Visakhapatnam, was formed.

The Third Phase: 1970-78

Another important Committee which went into various aspects of Panchayati Raj institutions in Andhra Pradesh was set up in 1971. It was headed by C.Narasimham. The Committee was asked to review the functioning of Panchayati Raj institutions in the light of the experience gained during the twelve years of its existence. It submitted its report in 1972, with the following recommendations.³⁷

1. The Sarpanch of a village panchayat should be directly elected by all the voters in the village, and the continuation of electing the vice-sarpanch by the sarpanch and the members of the village panchayat.
2. A Panchayati Samiti should be composed only with the directly elected members and Sarpanches, elected by an electoral system and members of Gram Panchayat and the strength of its members should be fixed for twelve times to the number of members elected to the Zilla Parishad.
3. The President and Vice-President of the Samiti should be elected by all the members of the Samiti from among themselves.
4. The Zilla Parishad should consist of all the members directly elected from the single member constituencies (subjected to a limit of four per block) into which the blocks were to be divided, with the Presidents of the Samities as its ex-officio members.
5. The practice of associating the District Collector as ex-officio member and chairperson of the standing committee of the parishad should be dispensed with.
6. The no-confidence motion against the Sarpanch of the village panchayat should not be allowed as he was elected directly. However, but this provision is applicable in case of Vice-Sarpanch.
7. For the Gram Panchayati, one to three seats are reserved for women depending on their strength in the village panchayat. The Committee felt that there is no need for reservation of seats for women in the Samiti and Zilla Parishads. However political parties can choose as many women as possible and give them proper representation.
8. One seat should be reserved either for S.Cs or S.Ts in the Village Panchayat if there are at least ten voters among them in a given panchayat, and in the Zilla Parishad according to the percentage of their population in the district.
9. Legislators need not be made as ex-officio members either of the Samiti or the Parishad.
10. The existing standing committees of the Panchayati Samiti should be re-designated as subject committees, limited to four in number: (i) planning, agriculture and industry; (ii) education; (iii) social welfare; and (iv) women's welfare.
11. Political parties should be recognised for the purpose of elections to the Zilla Parishads and Panchayat Samities. The District Development Fund should be constituted and administered by the Zilla Parishad. Instead of giving grants-in-aid to panchayat raj bodies on various items, a block grant of twenty-five crores (two hundred and fifty million) rupees every year may be given.

The Committee had strongly recommended for setting up of a Local Authority Finance Commission for every five years on the basis of the National Finance Commission. The authorities should be entrusted with government, to remove a Sarpanch, Vice-Sarpanch or a member of the Gram Panchayati.

Till 1976, no major changes took place in the Panchayat Raj system in Andhra Pradesh. Keeping in view of the recommendations of the J. Vengala Rao Committee (1968) and the C. Narasimham Committee (1972), the state government amended the Gram Panchayati Act of 1964 and the Panchayati Samities and Zilla Parishads Act of 1959 in 1976 and 1978 respectively.

Gram Panchayat Amendment Acts of 1976-1978

The Andhra Pradesh Gram Panchayat (Amendment) Act, 1976, raised the minimum strength of the Gram Panchayat from five to seven and the maximum from seventeen to nineteen members. One seat was reserved for the S.Cs or S.Ts, if their population was 25 percent or less. If their population was more than 25 percent but less than 50 percent, the seats were reserved for the above mentioned proportionately according to their population.³⁸

Under the amendment, the Sarpanch should be elected directly by all the voters of the panchayat. The election of the Sarpanch, the President of the Panchayati Samiti and the members of the Gram Panchayati should be conducted at the same time. The Sarpanch should not be removed by the Gram Panchayat. The State Government can remove him from office, if the sarpanch fails to perform his duties. There had been reports of clashes between the Sarpanch and the members in the Gram Panchayat leading to operational problems.

According to the amendment made in 1978 the Samiti President should be directly elected by all the voters in the Samiti area. The government only could remove the President of the Panchayat samiti if he failed to discharge his duties. Members of the State Legislature are not eligible to hold the office of the President.

With the 1978 amendment, the Samiti consisted of: (a) the President, (b) the Sarpanches of the Gram Panchayats within the Samiti area, and (c) the M.L.As and M.L.Cs who are its registered voters. The above members will elect six members. Among them two are women, one each from the S.Cs and S.Ts and the two persons belonging to the backward classes. The Government would nominate one person each from the following categories i.e., the backward classes, the minorities, those working for cooperatives, and social workers. These nominated members don't have the right to elect the Vice-President or to vote in the standing committees. The standing committees were reduced from seven to five i.e., development, education, social welfare, works and finance.

The composition of the Zilla Parishad was also changed in accordance with the 1978 amendment. The Collector was disassociated from holding the membership in the Zilla Parishad and the post of Chairperson in the Standing Committees. However, he continues to assume supervisory powers over the Gram Panchayat and the Panchayat Samiti as an agent of the State Government.

A few important changes took place in the Panchayat raj system through the 1976 and 1978 Amendment Acts. These included the reduction of the age to get the right to vote from twenty-one to eighteen, and reservation fixed for the S.Ts and S.Cs for elective posts in respect of the Sarpanch of the Gram Panchayat and President of the panchayat samits respectively.

Fourth Phase: 1979-85 This phase was marked by two important developments namely, the appointment of the State Committee on Panchayat Raj and the holding of elections to Panchayat bodies after a gap of a decade.

A Committee chaired by C.Narasimham was appointed in 1979 to review the problems faced by Panchayat Raj institutions and consider the implications of the Ashok Mehta Committee.

The Committee felt that Panchayat Raj bodies during the twenty years of their existence have passed through various phases: a phase of dynamism, 1959-64; a phase of stagnation, 1965-69; and a phase of decline, 1970 onwards. They have not been managed comprehensively for almost a decade and ultimately the Zilla Parishads and Panchayati Samits have been superseded and put under official control. Elections to Panchayat Raj bodies were not held for about a decade.

The Committee recommended for the provision of constitutional safeguards to the Panchayat Assembly. It emphasized the need for one on the lines of incorporating a special article defining the goals and objectives of these bodies. That special Article is Article 242. This Article made obligation for the state to establish, organise and encourage local bodies with adequate funds, powers and functions. It also recommended for setting up of a State Finance commission to deal with the finances of Panchayat. However no significant attempts were made on the above suggestions.

The Final Phase: 1986-Up Date

The next attempt regarding the Panchayat Raj institutions was made in 1986. The Telugu Desam Government, which came to power in 1983, made a promise in its election manifesto that it would work for the revitalization of Panchayat Raj institutions. It accorded importance to decentralized planning and administration, with a view to make the Panchayat Raj institutions closer to the people.

The initial thinking of the state government was for reorganizing the three-tier system into two tiers, in tune with the Ashok Mehta Committee report. The idea was to retain the old Zilla Parishads and establish Mandal Panchayats in the place of the Panchayati Samities and Gram Panchayats. (Since this proposal was not approved, it was decided to introduce a four-tier system, that is, the Gram Panchayats the Mandal Praja Parishad and the Zilla Parishad and Zilla Pranalika Abhivrudhi Sameeksha Mandali (District Planning and Development Council-DPDC). The Andhra Pradesh Mandala Praja Parishads, Zilla Praja Praishads and Zilla Pranalika Abhivrudhi Sameeksha Mandals Act, 1986, came into effect from January of the following year.

Efforts were also made to bring about changes in the organisation of the Gram Panchayats. As already stated, the initial thinking was to do away with the Gram Panchayats altogether and establish Mandals as adjuncts to the Mandal Parishad. However, due to the criticism from within and outside the ruling party, the Gram Panchayats were left intact. They continued to be governed by the 1964 Act.

The 1986 Act

The 1986 Act made significant changes in the Panchayati Raj setup. It abolished 330 Panchayat Samits and created 1,104 Mandala Praja Parishads (M.P.Ps) in their place. While a Gram Panchayati had been constituted for a village, the Mandala Praja Parishad was created for a group of villages with the population of thirty-five to fifty thousand, and the Zilla Parishad, renamed as Zilla Praja Parishad, was made coterminous with the district. The size of the middle unit was reduced by one-third; roughly three to four Mandala Praja Parishads for each Panchayati Samiti were created, with the proclaimed aim of taking administration "nearer" to the people (prajalavaddaku palana). It was aimed at developing these units of a decentralized administrative system where all important departments like revenue, police, cooperation, education, health agriculture etc work with coordination. They were entrusted with the powers and functions of the erstwhile Panchayat Samits.

The Sarpanches, M.L.As and M.Ps were made as ex-officio members of the Mandala Praja Parishads. A new provision for co-option of a member from the linguistic or religious minorities to the M.P.P. was also made in the 1986 Act. It indicated that the President is elected directly by the registered voters of the Mandal. Besides, the reservation of 15 percent and 6 percent respectively for the S.Cs and S.Ts and the quota of reservation to backward classes and women was 33.3 percent respectively within quota of 50 percent. Thus, the total reservation quota was raised from 21 percent to 50 percent.

The President of the Mandal Parishad can convene, preside over and conduct the meetings of the Mandal Parishad. He could exercise administrative control over the Mandal Parishad Development Officer (MPDO). The major sources of income for the Mandal Parishad were governmental grants and funds relating to various schemes. It also receives a share of the land revenue and other state taxes. The State Government can remove the President or the Vice-President of a Mandal if he misuses his powers or refuses to carry out its orders.

The Zilla Praja Parishad (Z.P.P.)

The Chairperson of the Zilla Praja Parishad (Z.P.P) is directly elected by the voters of the district and there are twenty-two Z.P.Ps in the State. Out of them, ten Z.P.P were reserved for the weaker sections. They are as follows:

Scheduled Tribes, 1; Scheduled Castes, 3; Backward Classes, 4; women, 2. All the presidents of the MPPs in the district, as well as M.L.As and M.Ps of the district were members of the Zilla Praja Parishad. One member belonging to either a linguistic or religious minority will be co-opted. The District Collector will be the ex-office member.

Zilla Pranalika Abhivrudhi Sameeksha Mandal

Each district, excluding Hyderabad, had a statutory Zilla Pranalika Abhivrudhi Sameeksha Mandal. The Chairman of the Z.P.P is conferred with the status of the Minister of the State. He is entrusted with some advisory functions. He reviews the developmental activities undertaken by the Z.P.P. from time to time. This body will be headed by a Minister nominated by the Chief Minister. The Z.P.P. Chairperson, the District Collector, all the legislators from the district and some members belonging to experts are nominated by the government. The District Collector is the member –secretary. Due to criticism from the public about the creation of such a nominated body over the Z.P.P., the Government had initially thought of lowering the position of the Z.P.A.S.M. But it could not do so due to the considerable pressure from the ministers and legislations of the state.

Andhra Pradesh Panchayati Raj Act-1994

The State Government made some amendments to the existing laws concerning the Panchayat (which is discussed in the previous chapter) Raj Institutions in the light of the Constitutional (73rd Amendment) Act. According to the Act, Andhra Pradesh Panchayat Raj Bill was passed by the State Legislative Assembly on March 30, 1994. The new Act, called the Andhra Pradesh Panchayati Raj Act, 1994 came into force on May 30 1994, by replacing the earlier Acts. In accordance with the provisions of the Act a three tier structure comprising of Zilla Parishad at the district level, Mandal Praja Parishad at the intermediate level and Gram Panchayat at the village level were constituted in the State. Since then the Act has been amended from time to time during the last ten years of its operation to make it more effective.

Important features of A.P. Panchayati Raj Act of 1994

The following are some important features of A.P. Panchyati Raj Act, 1994.

1. Provision of organic linkage among the three tiers for enabling the Sarpanches of the Gram Panchayats to attend the General Body meeting of the Mandal Parishad. Similarly, the Presidents of the Mandal Parishad are entitled to attend the General Body meetings of the Zilla Parishad without the right to vote on the resolution.
2. Provision of the norm of two children, whereby a candidate with more than two children will be disqualified to contest in the elections or to continue as a member in any one of the Panchayati Raj bodies.
3. A member who is absent for three consecutive meetings is deemed to be disqualified thereby to ensure the regularity of the members of the functioning of Panchayats.
4. Joint cheque power for the operation of Gram Panchayats fund is provided to the Sarpanch of the Gram Panchayat along with a member purposively selected by the Gram Panchayat.
5. The scheme of selection of Gram Panchayats is another unique feature in the State. Committees have been formed at the State, District and Mandal level for the selection of best Gram Panchyats and inducements are provided to stimulate the panchayats.
6. The Power to call for information from the Village Development Officer (VDO) has been entrusted to the Gram Panchayats.
7. Co-option to minorities given to provide representation to all sections including the community in the village, and
8. Provision for bringing no-confidence motion against the heads of Panchayati Raj Institutions only once in their five year term, not in the first two years after holding of the office.

We have seen how the Panchayat Raj System has been reformed and improved upon by the governments of the day to make it more responsive and cater to the needs of the requirements of the society. We shall now discuss how backward Classes political participation has been growing by years at country level, state level and more particularly at the Local bodies level

Table - 2.3

District Level Elected Backward Castes Representatives of Andhra Pradesh in Zilla Parishad Local Body Elections 2001, 2006 and 2014

Elected as	Total in 2001	B.C	Total in 2006	B.C	Total in 2014	B.C
a. ZP Chairpersons	22	07	22	08	22	07
b. ZP Vice Chairpersons	22	05	22	09	22	08
c. ZPTC Members	1,098	366	1,098	347	1,098	363

Source: Election Commission of A.P State

The Table 2.3 throws light on the backward caste representatives elected to the local body elections (Zilla Parishads) in the years 2001, 2006 and 2014. In the 2001 elections conducted to the Zilla Parishads, out of 22 Zilla Parishads Chairpersons, seven chairpersons were from backward castes. Likewise, out of 22 Zilla Parishads' Vice- chairpersons, 5 were from backward castes. Out of 1098 ZPTC Members 366 belonged to the backward castes.

Similarly, in the year 2006, elections were conducted to the Zilla Parishads. Out of 22 Zilla Parishad Chairpersons, eight persons were from backward castes and out of 22 Zilla Parishads Vice-chairpersons, 9 were from backward castes. Out of 1098 ZPTC Members, 347 were from backward castes. In the year 2014, elections were conducted to the Zilla Parishads. Out of 22 Zilla Parishad Chairperson posts, 7 were occupied by the backward castes and similarly out of 22 zilla Parishad Vice-chairperson posts, eight posts were occupied by the backward castes.. And out of 1098 ZPTC members, 363 belong to the backward castes

Table - 2.4

Mandal Level Elected Backward Castes Representatives of Andhra Pradesh in Mandal Parishad Local Body Elections 2001, 2006 and 2014

Elected as	Total in 2001	B.C	Total in 2006	B.C	Total in 2014	B.C
a. M.P.Ps	1,098	371	1,098	431	1,098	347
b. MPTCs	16,589	5918	16,589	6437	16,148	6095

Source: Election Commission of A.P State

The Table 2.4 depicts the backward castes representation in the Mandal Parishads. In the year 2001, elections were conducted to the Mandal Parishads. Out of 1098 Mandal Presidents, 371 representatives were from backward castes. In the 2006 elections conducted to the Mandal Parishads, out of 1098 Mandal Presidents, 431 belong to the backward castes. Similarly, out of 16589 MPTCs, 6437 belong to the backward castes. In the year 2014, elections were conducted to the Mandal Parishads. Out of 1098 Mandal President posts, 347 were occupied by people belonging to backward class. Similarly, out of 16, 148 posts of MPTCs, 6095 were occupied by the people belonging to the backward castes.

Table - 2.5

Village Level Elected Backward Caste Representatives of Andhra Pradesh in Local Body Village Panchayats Elections 2006 and 2014.

District Level

Elected as	Total in 2006	B.C	Total in 2014	B.C
a. Village Sarpanches	21,469	10911	21,649	11524
b. Ward Members	2,17,789	137276	2,18,208	146524

Source: Election Commission of A.P State

The Table 2.5 depicts the Backward Castes representation in the Village Panchayats. In the local body elections held in 2006, out of 21, 469 village Sarpanches 10911 were from backward classes. Likewise, in the local body elections held in 2014, out of 21, 649 village sarpanches who are elected, 11524 belonged to backward classes. Out of 2, 17, 789 Ward members who were elected in the local body elections of 2006, 13 72 76 were from backward classes. Likewise, in the local body elections conducted in 2014, out of 2,18, 208, 146 524 were from the backward classes.

Table - 2.6

District Wise Backward Caste Representatives Elected As ZP Chairpersons of Andhra Pradesh in 2001 Elections

S.No.	Name	Caste	District	Party affiliation
1.	G.Thipe swamy	BC	Ananthapuramu	TDP
2.	M.Reddemma	BC(W)	Chittoor	INC
3.	K.Suresh Babu	BC	Cuddapha	INC
4.	B.Venkata Ramudu	BC	Kurnool	TDP
5.	Keeth Lakshamma	BC(W)	Nalgonda	INC
6.	Chenchal Babu	BC	Nellore	INC
7.	Kasani Gnaeswar	BC	Ranga Reddy	TDP

Source: Election Commission of A.P State

In the 2001 local body elections, elections are conducted to 22 Zilla Parishads. Out of 22 Z.P Chairman posts, seven BC candidates were elected as Zilla Parishad Chairpersons. Among them, there was also two women representative. Out of the seven backward class Zilla Parishad Chairpersons, three belonged to the Telugu Desam party and the rest four belonged to the Indian National Congress.

Table - 2.7

District Wise Backward Caste Representatives Elected as ZP Vice-Chairpersons of Andhra Pradesh in 2001 Elections

S.No.	Name	Caste	District	Party affiliation
1.	Siddineni. Kotaiah	BC	Khammam	CPM
2.	Badini Chennaiah	BC	Nalgonda	CPM
3.	Ponthangal M. Kishan Rao	BC	Nizamabad	TRS
4.	Nanda Kumar Yadaav	BC	Ranga Reddy	BJP
5.	Sambari Samma Rao	BC	Warangal	INC

Source: Election Commission of A.P State

In the year 2001 elections conducted to the local bodies, there were five backward class candidates who were elected as Vice-chairpersons out of 22 candidates for the post of Vice-Chairpersons. Among them, two belonged to CPM, and one each were elected from TRS, BJP, INC.

Table – 2.8

District Wise Backward Caste Representatives Elected as ZP Chairpersons of Andhra Pradesh in 2006 Elections

S.No.	Name	Caste	District	Part affiliation
1.	S. Venugopala Krishana	BC	East Godavari	INC
2.	K.Venkata Nageswar Rao	BC	West Godavari	INC
3.	Gonela Vijayalakshmi	BC	Khammam	INC
4.	K.Nageswar Rao	BC	Krishana	INC
5.	Rajashekarm palavalasa	BC	Srikakulam	INC
6.	Katam Aruna	BC	Prakasam	INC
7.	G. Ramamurthy	BC	Vishakapatnam	INC
8.	Bosta Jhansi	BC (Turupu kapu)	Vizianagaram	INC

Source: Election Commission of A.P State

In the year 2006, local body elections were conducted to 22 Zilla Parishads. Out of 22 Z.P Chairman posts, 8 BC candidates were elected as Zilla Parishads Chairpersons. Among them, there were also 3 women representatives. All the backward class leaders who were elected as Zilla Parishad Chairpersons belonged to only Indian National Congress.

Table – 2.9

District Wise Backward Caste Representatives Elected as ZP Vice-Chairpersons of Andhra Pradesh in 2006 Elections

S.No.	Name	Caste	District	Part affiliation
1	Muddala Narsimhulu	BC	Ananthapuramu	INC
2	Tegala Ravinder Goud	BC	Karimnagar	TRS
3	Ayodhya Chary Bollaju	BC	Khammam	CPI
4	M. Krishana	BC	Mahaboob Nagar	INC
5	G.Pandari	BC	Naglonda	CPI
6	T.V.Subba Raja	BC	Nellore	INC
7	Kasani Swetha	BC	Ranga Reddy	TDP
8	Duvvada Srinivas	BC	Srikakulam	INC
9	Moluguri Bixapathi	BC	Warangal	TRS

Source: Election Commission of A.P State

In the 2006 elections conducted to the local bodies, there were 9 backward class candidates who were elected as Vice-chairpersons out of 22 candidates for the post of Vice-chairpersons. There were 2 women candidates who were elected as Zilla Parishad Vice-chairpersons. Among them, 4 belonged to Indian National

Congress, 2 belonged to TRS, 2 belonged to CPI and One candidate belonged to the Telugu Desam Party.

Table – 2.10

District Wise Backward Caste Representatives Elected as ZP Chairpersons Of Andhra Pradesh in 2014 Elections

S.No.	Name	Caste	District	Party affiliation
1.	Vallikonda Sobha Rani	BC(W)	Adilabad	TRS
2.	Thula Uma	BC(W)	Kharimnagar	TRS
3.	Erragolla Rajamani	BC(W)	Medak	TRS
4.	Raju Dafedar	BC	Nizamabad	TRS
5.	D.Chaman Sab	BC	Ananthapuramu	TDP
6.	Shaik Jani Moon	BC	Guntur	TDP
7.	M.Rajasekhar	BC	Kurnool	YSRCP

Source: Election Commission of A.P State

From the above table we can gather that in the 2014 local body elections, elections were conducted to 22 Zilla Parishads. Out of 22 Z.P Chairman posts, seven BC candidates were elected as Zilla Parishad Chairpersons. Among them, there were 3 women representatives. Out of the seven backward class Zilla Parishad Chairpersons, 2 belonged to the Telugu Desam Party, 4 belonged TRS and 1 belonged to YSRCP.

Table – 2.11

District Wise Backward Caste Representatives Elected as ZP Vice-Chairpersons of Andhra Pradesh in 2014 Elections

S.No.	Name	Caste	District	Party affiliation
1	J.pushpavathi	BC(W)	Kurnool	TDP
2	Nukasani Balaji	BC	Prakasham	YSRCP
3	Pottella Siresha	BC(W)	SPSR Nellore	YSRCP
4	Khandapu Jyothi	BC(W)	Srikakulam	TDP
5	Kotyada Apparao	BC	Vishakapatnam	TDP
6	Balagam Krishna Murthy	BC	Vizianagaram	TDP
7	Chettupally Muralidhar	BC	Warangal	TDP
8	Chintala Venkata Ramana	BC	West Godavari	TDP

Source: Election Commission of A.P State

From the above table we can understand that in the 2014 elections conducted to the local bodies, there were 8 backward class candidates who were elected as Vice-chairpersons out of 22 candidates for the post of Vice-chairpersons. There were 3 women candidates who were elected as Zilla Parishad Vice-chairpersons. Among them, 2 were elected from YSRC and, 6 candidates belonged to the Telugu Desam Party.

Table – 2.12

**District Wise Backward Caste Representatives in
Andhra Pradesh in 2001 ZPTC Elections**

S.No	Name of the District	TDP	INC	TRS	CPI(M)	Others	Total
1	Adilabad	12	3	0	-	0	15
2	Ananthapuramu	9	9	0	-	2	20
3	Chittoor	10	9	0	-	0	19
4	Kadapa	6	8	0	-	0	14
5	Guntur	7	8	0	-	0	15
6	East Godavari	10	2	0	-	2	14
7	Karimnagar	2	12	5	-	1	20
8	Khammam	2	6	0	-	2	10
9	Krishana	11	3	0	-	0	14
10	Kurnool	9	8	0	-	1	18
11	Mahaboobnagar	14	9	2	-	0	25
12	Medak	3	10	5	-	0	18
13	Nalgond	4	9	2	6	1	22
14	Nellore	4	9	0	-	0	13
15	Nizamabad	1	5	9	-	0	15
16	West Godavari	9	6	0	-	0	15
17	Warngal	5	7	7	-	1	20
18	Viziayanagaramu	9	9	0	-	0	18
19	Vishakapatnam	6	7	0	-	0	13
20	Srikakulam	16	4	0	-	1	21
21	Ranga Reddy	3	7	1	-1	2	14
22	Prakasham	6	7	0	-	0	13
	Grand Total	158	157	31	7	10	366

Source: Election Commission of A.P State

From the above table we can conclude that 366 backward class candidates were elected as ZPTC members from out of a total of 1098 ZPTC constituencies.

We can also gather from the table that 158 backward class candidates were elected as ZPTC members on Telugu Desam Party ticket. Likewise, 157 were elected as representatives of Indian National Congress. Similarly, 31 candidates were elected on TRS Party ticket. 7 were elected from CPM and 10 candidates were elected from other parties. Thus a total of 366 candidates belonging to backward classes were elected as ZPTC members out of 1098 ZPTC constituencies.

Table – 2.13

**District Wise Backward Caste Representatives in Andhra Pradesh
in 2001 MPP Elections**

S.No	Name of the District	TDP	INC	TRS	Others	Total
1	Adilabad	9	4	3	0	16
2	Ananthapuramu	9	11	0	0	20
3	Chittoor	8	10	0	0	18
4	Kadapa	4	9	0	0	13
5	Guntur	7	6	0	0	13
6	East Godavari	10	4	0	3	17
7	Karimnagar	7	5	8	3	23
8	Khammam	3	4	3	0	10
9	Krishana	6	8	0	1	15
10	Kurnool	13	5	0	1	19
11	Mahaboobnagar	11	12		2	25
12	Medak	4	6	7	1	18
13	Nalgonda	3	11	3	6	23
14	Nellore	5	4	0	3	12
15	Nizamabad	3	4	8	1	16
16	West Godavari	10	4	0	0	14
17	Warngal	6	7	6	1	20
18	Vizayanagaramu	10	8	0	0	18
19	Vishakapatnam	6	4	0	2	12
20	Srikakulam	12	8	0	1	21
21	Ranga Reddy	6	7	1	0	14
22	Prakasam	6	7	0	1	14
	Grand Total	158	148	39	26	371

Source: Election Commission of A.P State

From the above table we can conclude that 371 backward class candidates were elected as Mandal Parishad Presidents from out of a total of 1098 MPP constituencies.

We can also gather from the table that 158 backward class candidates were elected as MPPS on Telugu Desam Party ticket. Likewise, 148 were elected as representatives of Indian National Congress. Similarly, 39 candidates were elected on TRS party ticket and 26 belonged to other parties. Thus, a total of 371 candidates belonging to backward classes were elected as MPPs out of 1098 MPP constituencies.

Table – 2.14

**District Wise Backward Caste Representatives in Andhra Pradesh
in 2006 ZPTC Elections**

S.No	Name of the District	TDP	INC	TRS	CPM	Others	Total
1	Adilabad	14	6	-	-		20
2	Ananthapuramu	6	12	-	-		18
3	Chittoor	5	12	--	-		17
4	Kadapa	0	11	-	--	1	12
5	Guntur	0	11	-	-	1	12
6	East Godavari	7	13	-	-		20
7	Karimnagar	10	13	2	-	0	25
8	Khammam	2	4	1	-	3	10
9	Krishana	5	9	-	-		14
10	Kurnool	4	13	-	-	1	18
11	Mahaboobnagar	10	12	2	-		24
12	Medak	11	5	3	-		19
13	Nalgond	6	10	1	-	6	23
14	Nellore	4	7	-	-	-	11
15	Nizamabad	3	9	3	-	-	15
16	West Godavari	6	8	-	-	-	14
17	Warngal	10	8	1	-	1	20
18	Viziyanagaramu	5	9	-	-	-	14
19	Vishakapatnam	6	5	-	-	-	11
20	Srikakulam	7	14	-	-	-	21
21	Ranga Reddy	5	9	-	-	-	14
22	Prakasm	2	12	-	-	1	15
	Grand Total	128	212	13	-	14	367

Source: Election Commission of A.P State

From the above table we can conclude that 367 backward class candidates were elected as ZPTC members from out of a total of 1098 ZPTC constituencies.

We can also gather from the table that 128 backward class candidates were elected as ZPTC members on Telugu Desam Party ticket. Likewise, 212 were elected as representatives of Indian National Congress. Similarly, 13 candidates were elected on TRS party ticket. And 14 belonged to other parties. Thus, a total of 367 candidates belonging to backward classes were elected as ZPTC members out of 1098 ZPTC constituencies.

Table – 2.15

**District Wise Backward Caste Representatives in Andhra Pradesh
in 2006 MPP Elections**

S.No	Name of the District	TDP	INC	TRS	Others	Total
1	Adilabad	12	7	0	2	21
2	Ananthapuramu	14	8	0	1	23
3	Chittoor	6	13	0	0	19
4	Kadapa	0	11	0	0	11
5	Guntur	0	11	0	0	11
6	East Godavari	8	7	0	1	16
7	Karimnagar	12	11	2	3	28
8	Khammam	4	6	0	2	12
9	Krishana	9	7	0	1	17
10	Kurnool	6	11	0	3	20
11	Mahaboobnagar	13	17	0	0	30
12	Medak	10	12	3	1	26
13	Nalgonda	10	12	0	7	29
14	Nellore	4	9	0	1	14
15	Nizamabad	7	10	0	0	17
16	West Godavari	6	9	0	0	15
17	Warngal	3	15	0	3	21
18	Viziayanagaramu	11	16	0	0	27
19	Vishakapatnam	5	10	0	0	15
20	Srikakulam	6	27	0	0	33
21	Ranga Reddy	8	2	0	0	10
22	Prakasham	4	12	0	0	16
	Grand Total	158	243	5	25	431

Source: Election Commission of A.P State

From the above table we can conclude that 431 backward class candidates were elected as Mandal Parishad Presidents from out of a total of 1098 MPP constituencies.

We can also gather from the above table that 158 backward class candidates were elected as MPSS on Telugu Desam Party ticket. Likewise, 243 were elected as representatives of Indian National Congress. Similarly, 05 candidates were elected on TRS party ticket. And 25 belonged to other parties. Thus a total of 431 candidates belonging to backward classes were elected as MPPs out of 1098 MPP constituencies.

Table – 2.16

**District Wise Backward caste Representatives in Andhra Pradesh
in 2006 MPTC Elections**

S.No	Name of the District	TDP	INC	TRS		Others	Total
1	Adilabad	105	86	18		13	222
2	Ananthapuramu	160	149	0	0	8	317
3	Chittoor	109	187	0	0	9	305
4	Kadapa	34	72	0	0	0	106
5	Guntur	68	163	0	0	10	241
6	East Godavari	201	160	0	0	9	370
7	Karimnagar	155	145	47		22	369
8	Khammam	42	56	1		51	150
9	Krishana	136	153	0	0	20	309
10	Kurnool	130	197	0	0	37	364
11	Mahaboobnagar	193	203	7		26	429
12	Medak	134	121	40		30	325
13	Nalgonda	121	159	13	0	97	390
14	Nellore	84	101	0	0	20	205
15	Nizamabad	111	114	19	0	17	261
16	West Godavari	150	173	0	0	17	340
17	Warngal	49	48	13		9	119
18	Vizayanagaramu	111	203	0	0	6	320
19	Vishakapatnam	118	159	0	0	8	285
20	Srikakulam	121	335	0	0	6	462
21	Ranga Reddy	111	69	7	0	79	266
22	Prakasam	70	146	0	0	6	222
	Grand Total	2513	3199	165	0	560	6437

Source: Election Commission of A.P State

From the above table we can conclude that 6437 backward class candidates were elected as Mandal Parishad Territorial Constituency Members from out of a total of 16589 MPT Constituencies.

We can also gather from the above table that 2513 backward class candidates were elected as MPTCs on Telugu Desam Party ticket. Likewise, 3199 were elected as representatives of Indian National Congress. Similarly, 165 candidates were elected on TRS party ticket. And 560 belonged to other parties. Thus, a total of 6437 candidates belonging to backward classes were elected as MPTCs out of 16589 MPTC constituencies.

Table – 2.17
District Wise Backward Caste Representatives in Andhra Pradesh
in 2014 ZPTC Elections

S.No	Name of the District	TDP	INC	TRS	YSRP	Others	Total
1	Adilabad	1	0	13		2	16
2	Ananthapuramu	14	0		5	0	19
3	Chittoor	6	0		5		11
4	Kadapa	3	0		10	0	13
5	Guntur	9	0		3	0	12
6	East Godavari	18	0		2		20
7	Karimnagar	0	6	18		1	25
8	Khammam	3	3	0		3	9
9	Krishana	10	0		5		15
10	Kurnool	8	1		13	0	22
11	Mahaboobnagar	3	13	8			24
12	Medak	3	6	10			19
13	Nalgonda	0	17	6		0	23
14	Nellore	4			9		13
15	Nizamabad	0	5	11			16
16	West Godavari	15	0				15
17	Warngal	3	8	7		1	19
18	Viziayanagaramu	11	0		6		17
19	Vishakapatnam	6	0		4		10
20	Srikakulam	13	0		6		19
21	Ranga Reddy	3	5	5	0		13
22	Prakasam	8	0		5	0	13
	Grand Total	141	64	78	73	7	363

Source: Election Commission of A.P State

From the above table we can conclude that 363 backward class candidates were elected as ZPTC members from out of a total of 1098 ZPTC constituencies.

We can also gather from the table that 141 backward class candidates were elected as ZPTC members on Telugu Desam Party ticket. Likewise, 64 were elected as representatives of Indian National Congress. Similarly, 78 candidates were elected on TRS party ticket. 73 belonged to YSR CP and 7 candidates were elected from other parties. Thus a total of 363 candidates belonging to backward classes were elected as ZPTC members out of 1098 ZPTC constituencies.

Table – 2.18

**District Wise Backward castes Representatives in Andhra Pradesh
in 2014 MPP Elections**

S.No	Name of the District	TDP	INC	TRS	YSRC P	Others	Total
1	Adilabad	3	1	6		4	14
2	Ananthapuramu	18	0	0	1	0	19
3	Chittoor	11	0	0	7	0	18
4	YSR Kadapa	3	0	0	9	1	13
5	Guntur	10	0	0	2	0	12
6	East Godavari	17	0	0	1	0	18
7	Karimnagar	0	5	18		1	24
8	Khammam	pending	0	0		0	0
9	Krishana	8	0	0	5	0	13
10	Kurnool	10	0	0	11	0	21
11	Mahaboobnagar	8	5	8		3	24
12	Medak	2	8	8		0	18
13	Nalgonda	0	13	7	0	1	21
14	SPSR Nellore	5	0	0	6	2	13
15	Nizamabad	2	1	12		0	15
16	West Godavari	11	0	0	2	0	13
17	Warngal	4	8	5		0	17
18	Viziayanagaramu	12	0	0	5	0	17
19	Vishakapatnam	8	0	0	1	0	9
20	Srikakulam	15	0	0	7	0	22
21	Ranga Reddy	4	3	3	0	3	13
22	Prakasam	8	0	0	4	1	13
	Grand Total	159	44	67	61	26	347

Source: Election Commission of A.P State

From the above table we can conclude that 347 backward class candidates were elected as Mandal Parishad Presidents from out of a total of 1098 MPP constituencies.

We can also gather from the table that 159 backward class candidates were elected as MPPS on Telugu Desam party ticket. Likewise, 44 were elected as representatives of Indian National Congress. Similarly, 67 candidates were elected on TRS party ticket, 61 belonged to YSRCP and 26 belonged to other parties. Thus a total of 347 candidates belonging to backward classes were elected as MPPs out of 1098 MPP constituencies.

Table – 2.19

District Wise Backward Caste Representatives in Andhra Pradesh in 2014 MPTC Elections

S.No	Name of the District	TDP	INC	TRS	YSRP	Others	Total
1	Adilabad	15	51	57		34	157
2	Ananthapuramu	163	0		90	3	256
3	Chittoor	121	0		115	13	249
4	Kadap	36	0		95	0	131
5	Guntur	92	0		93	5	190
6	East Godavari	210	0		144	11	365
7	Karimnagar	36	202	245		108	591
8	Khammam	38	17	0	25	28	108
9	Krishana	116	0		84	13	213
10	Kurnool	112	0		162	35	309
11	Mahaboobnagar	70	154	115		53	392
12	Medak	106	264	214		71	655
13	Nalgonda	56	146	46		64	312
14	Nellore	62			80	4	146
15	Nizamabad	7	105	100		39	251
16	West Godavari	193	0		62	12	267
17	Warngal	38	101	90		17	246
18	Viziayanagaramu	164	0		74	48	286
19	Vishakapatnam	106	0		55	9	170
20	Srikakulam	168	0		117	22	307
21	Ranga Reddy	56	88	82	0	38	264
22	Prakasam	75	0		139	16	230
	Grand Total	2040	1128	949	1335	643	6095

Source: Election Commission of A.P State⁴⁷.

From the above table we can conclude that 6095 backward class candidates were elected as Mandal Parishad Territorial constituency members from out of a total of 16148 MPTC constituencies.

We can also gather from the table that 2040 backward class candidates were elected as MPTC members on Telugu Desam Party ticket. Likewise, 1128 were elected as representatives of Indian National Congress. Similarly, 949 candidates were elected on TRS party ticket, 1335 belonged to YSRCP and 643 belonged to other parties. Thus a total of 6059 candidates belonging to backward classes were elected as MPTCs out of 16148 MPTC constituencies.

Objectives of the Study

Keeping the study gaps in the earlier studies and need for the study in mind, the following issues are considered as main objectives of the study. To analyse the concept of the Backward Castes political participation in Panchayat raj institution and theories of representations for understanding the political participation and the representation patterns.

Methodology

The present study is based on both primary and secondary sources keeping in view the objectives of the research study. The primary data was collecting through the records. Most of the information is secured through administering. The secondary data is collected from the Gazettee records of Government of India and A.P, Reports of various studies and also from various books and journals pertaining to Backward Castes representation. Data is also collected from various national and regional news papers.

Hypothesis

1. There has been growing political awareness among the backward castes.

Scope of the Study

An attempt is made in this thesis to study the concept of Backward Castes rises and Political Participation in A.P

Need and Importance of study

selected for the purpose of studying the Back ward Caste political leadership. it is interesting to study the position and participation belonging to Backward Castes in the A.P politics. The Backward Caste population in the India, with its 46.1% share in the population largely resembles that of india 's Backward Caste population. Thus, it does not differ very much from the India in respect of demographic figures and the selection is very much relevant for the same appearance as the caste composition and population.

Analysis of data

In the present study various statistical methods and tools such as comparative percentage, diagrams used to analyse the available data.